

DESCRIPTION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical foundations of the development of the professional-creative competence of future teachers, in particular, the current issues, are studied. Also, theoretical-methodological aspects and tasks of increasing students' creativity and creativity were analyzed.

Key words: professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology, competence, creative, professional.

INTRODUCTION

The process of education and upbringing consists in preparing the growing young generation for life based on the social order that reflects the demands of society. In the process of education and training, young people acquire the knowledge, manners, customs, culture and labor skills collected by their ancestors, take their rightful place in society based on life experience, and the personality of a pedagogue in the formation of their potential and outlook. his professional skills are important. Determining the ways to develop the teacher's professional competence puts the issue of its determining factors in the first place.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Issues of formation and development of teacher's professional-creative competence V.A. Adolf, T.G. Braje, E.F. Zeera, I.A. Zimnyaya, N.V. Kuzmina, M.I. Lukyanova, A.K. Markova, A.M. Novikova, G.S. Trofimova, G. Bernhard, V. Bloom, H. Markus, It has been studied by many philosophers, pedagogues and psychologists such as R.Sterner.

The description of the factors affecting the development of professional competence is given in the works of I.A.Zimnya, E.F.Zeer, N.V.Kuzmina, A.K.Markova, L.M.Mitina, V.A.Slastenin and others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

The group of factors for changing the main activity includes the following - a change in the leading activity, a change in the method of activity implementation, in particular, its improvement. These factors have the greatest impact on the development of the activity component of professional competence. One of the most studied factors in Russian psychology is the change in leadership activity during the transition from one stage of development to

another. In the process of professional development, the change of leadership activity occurs at the stages of selection, professional training and professional adaptation. At the same time, it should be noted that with the professional development of the teacher, this factor loses its decisive importance. Undoubtedly, adult mental development takes place within the same activity. Therefore, the next factor is the change in the methods of carrying out activities within the same professional activity.

The second group of factors is represented by changes in the state of social development: changes in the socio-economic situation, conditions of the educational environment, situations in the implementation of professional plans, accidental events, etc. This group includes, first of all, factors that have the greatest impact on the development of the social and communicative component of the teacher's professional competence. A change in the social situation of development contributes to the development of professional competence, because it "forces" a person to change his usual behavior and encourages him to look for new opportunities for realization in the profession.

The next factor included in this group is the change in socio-economic living conditions. These include changes in the work of the educational institution, job cuts, salary changes, etc. Current socio-economic conditions can be considered extraordinary and "experimental". According to B.A. Sosnovsky, social instability affects "a person's orientation to time, the development of self-awareness, the level of professional skills, and intellectual capabilities" and increases the number of critical situations in a person's life.

The conditions of the educational environment, in particular, its innovative nature, is an important factor in this group. This is a set of various conditions necessary for the development of innovative educational activities in the school, a system of organizational forms and tools affecting innovative educational activities. Currently, the changes in the education system place new demands on the level of professional skills of teachers. In the current environment, teachers who develop professional competence in accordance with innovative changes will be competitive.

A factor in the development of professional competence can also be the expansion of the socio-professional environment as a result of immersion in professional activity. Business professionals, busy with work as a means of recognition and success, sometimes seriously violate professional ethics, are conflicted and show cruelty in relationships, but at the same time they have a very high level of professional competence. Finally, the factor of development of professional competence is accidental events and situations in the implementation of professional plans (for example, forced change of residence, reduction of workplace, etc.).

The third group of factors are the characteristics of the individual's subjectivity, which are determined by the internal conditions of personal development and the activities necessary for self-development. We identified such characteristics: increased social and professional activity, dissatisfaction with personal needs, readiness for professional self-determination, desire for self-development and self-realization, subjective feeling of stagnation in development and others. The factors included in this group have the greatest impact on the development of the personal component of the teacher's professional competence. A person's own activity is of great importance in the development of a person. The subjective activity of a person is constantly determined by the system of dominant needs, motives, interests, directions, etc.

One of the important factors determining the development of professional competence is social and professional activity. While carrying out professional activity, the teacher develops, develops his activity as he develops. However, if the activity begins to be strictly regulated, in this case, a person with a high level of activity will experience severe discomfort and dissatisfaction with his position in the workplace. The subjective feeling of self-satisfaction and continuous development initiates the development of professional competence. There comes a time when the further development of professional activity and the formation of its individual style is impossible without fundamentally changing the normatively approved activity. A teacher must act professionally and perform above the standard. Extreme professional activity can be manifested in the transition to a new level of education and skills or a qualitatively new, innovative level of activity.

Increased social and professional activity can also be a factor of professional competence. However, this factor appears at later stages of professional development. The development of pedagogical stagnation depends on the teacher's concentration. The lowest level of stagnation is observed among teachers of humanistic and cognitive (methodical) concentration. Stagnation also affects the experience of the teacher: the transfer of knowledge, abilities, skills that have become the property of society, by teaching certain educational materials according to a relatively stable program every year and using the same teaching technologies. will help. As a result, the development of professional competence also stops. In this case, we can say that the development of professional competence is an important factor in preventing the stagnation of the teacher's professional development.

Among the identified factors, the most important is, first of all, the conditions of the educational environment, that is, its innovative nature. After all, it is precisely the innovative educational environment that involves the active implementation of the teacher's professional activity, which in turn implies the development of professional competence.

CONCLUSION

The issue of competence and its place in society are the subject of many debates. The teacher's acquisition of high professional skills is carried out directly through the continuous education system. Professional development, which occupies the main place in the continuous education system, allows to analyze the student's activity and give him prospective directions. The current era requires a teacher to correctly understand the requirements of advanced pedagogical technology of teaching, to be proactive, to be aware of the news in his subject and to be able to introduce it into his classes.

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